

ANALYZING THE WAY ESL STUDENTS ENGAGE IN CONVERSATIONS: A STUDY ON TURN-TAKING PATTERNS

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ABSTRACT

This study employed qualitative analysis to scrutinize the turn-taking patterns of ESL (English as a Second Language) students in classroom settings. The researchers investigated how ESL students and their ESL teacher took turns during the second term of the 2023–2024 school year at National University-Manila. Analysis of transcribed discourse identified various turn-taking patterns among ESL students and their instructor. Findings revealed that, alongside challenges like managing overlapping speech and overcoming cultural differences, common turn-taking patterns included recognition overlap, terminal overlap, choral overlap, competitive overlap, continuers, cooperative overlap, progressional overlap, transitional overlap, and conditional access to turns. The predominant turn-taking strategy observed involves the use of transitional cues, such as pauses or intonation patterns, to signal transitions between speaking turns. Additionally, self-selection of turns is common, with participants frequently opting to speak following brief periods of silence. ESL learners encountered challenges in deciphering transitional cues, managing overlapping speech, and adapting to culturally diverse conversational norms. Both verbal and nonverbal cues, such as raising hands, maintaining eye contact, and actively listening to others, served as indicators of one's intent to speak. Drawing from these results, recommendations are provided for ESL educators and administrators to implement targeted interventions and instructional approaches aimed at supporting ESL students in their language acquisition journey.

Keywords: *ESL students, turn-taking patterns, classroom discourse, conversational patterns, challenges, strategies, and communication competence*

INTRODUCTION

For many years, linguists and academics have been captivated with the study of language acquisition and communication. This interest originates from the work of renowned people like Noam Chomsky, whose seminal contributions transformed our comprehension of language structure and acquisition mechanisms. Chomsky's theories—in particular, his notion of universal grammar—provided a basis for further studies in ESL teaching by examining how people learn and use language. Prominent individuals like Dale Carnegie, whose timeless ideas presented in "How to Win Friends and Influence People" are still relevant to language learners and professionals worldwide, have long promoted effective communication skills. For ESL students overcoming language and cultural hurdles, Carnegie's focus on empathy, active listening, and interpersonal communication emphasizes the need of learning effective communication in attaining personal and professional success.

Scholars such as Deborah Tannen and Erving Goffman pioneered the subject of discourse analysis, which provides essential insights into the complex dynamics of communication. Discourse analysts have been inspired in identifying the underlying patterns and structures that define spoken and written discourse by Tannen's groundbreaking research on conversational styles and Goffman's investigation of interaction rituals. Through their contributions, we now have a better knowledge of how language operates in social circumstances and a framework for researching communication tactics and turn-taking behaviors.

According to Uvaniv (2009), there are five distinct domains of discourse analysis that may be identified in relation to language teaching: cohesion, coherence, information structure, turn-taking, and critical discourse analysis (Celce-Murcia & Olshtain, 2000, p. 7). It is noteworthy that Norman Fairclough (2003, p. 3) proposes a distinction between discourse analysis that is focused on textual aspects and discourse analysis that is not focused on them.

To Fairclough (2003, p. 4), there is a strong tradition of using the phrase "critical discourse analysis" without taking into account the text's linguistic qualities, which are crucial for language instruction. Fairclough (2003) attempts, but ultimately fails, to bring these two discourse analysis philosophies together under the banner of "critical discourse analysis" in his book *Analyzing Discourse: Textual Analysis for Social Research*. For this reason, rather than Critical Discourse Analysis in EFL Reading, the degree project is called Discourse Analysis in EFL Reading.

The sociologists Harold Garfinkel and Harvey Sacks' explanation of the idea of turn-taking in discussions has played a significant role in influencing our comprehension of interactional dynamics. Sacks's groundbreaking work in *Conversation Analysis* and Garfinkel's ethnomethodological approach have given scholars analytical tools to study the mechanics behind conversational encounters. The foundation for researching turn-taking behaviors among ESL students has been laid by their turn-taking studies, which

have demonstrated the complex ways in which participants negotiate speaking turns and preserve coherence in conversation.

Turn-taking, a speech conversion system, is appropriate for a range of conversation patterns, according to Bingyang (2023). In an essay titled "A Simplest Systematics for the Organization of Turn-Taking for Conversation," Sacks and his colleagues develop a turn-taking system that consists of two parts: a description of the elements of turn and a set of rules. It was later incorporated into literary works and studied in institutional discourse in the early 1970s. Scholars have long been investigating the structure and function of turn-taking in discourse. With the development of new media, there has been a growing focus on interactions between people and computers as the primary mode of communication, leading to the emergence of WeChat language during these interactions. Turn-taking poses a fundamental challenge in discourse analysis, which can be applied to analyzing multiparty conversations on WeChat. Despite the widespread use of turn-taking systems in WeChat, multiparty conversations on the platform have received less attention compared to naturally occurring everyday conversations or comparative analyses using chat rooms.

The notion of "turn," initially introduced by American sociologist Harvey Sacks, has evolved over time along with the development of turn-taking theory. Sacks and his colleagues established the turn-taking system in 1974, which laid the foundational framework for everyday discourse, although the concept of a turn itself was not explicitly defined. This approach underscores the integral role of each turn, which may encompass words, phrases, clauses, or complete sentences. In the realm of daily discourse, as outlined in the *Journal of Linguistics and Communication Studies* 24, a turn serves as the fundamental unit of communication.

Shi (2023) conducted a literature review on turn-taking theory, which has garnered significant attention across various disciplines since its inception. Previous studies have predominantly focused on interpreting the definition and rules of turn-taking without deviating from Sacks' framework. Applications of turn-taking theory have been explored in various contexts such as news interviews, TV programs, classroom interactions, and daily dialogues, both domestically and internationally. However, there has been limited research on the turn features of WeChat language and multiparty conversations on WeChat. Through an analysis of the turn system in WeChat multiparty conversations, his study aimed to elucidate the characteristics of WeChat language and summarize its mechanisms.

According to Liu Hong (1992), it is the speaker's continuing speech at any point throughout the discussion, ending with the speaker and hearer switching roles, everyone falling silent, or the speaker giving a signal to stop speaking. The majority of academics in this discipline agreed with this definition. The entirety of a talk throughout a communication process makes up the turn.

There are two different ways to define turn, yet both have the same meaning. Willis Edmondson claims that there are two meanings associated with the term "turn." There

are two aspects to communication: the expression of the speaker, or what they say, and the possibility of becoming the speaker itself. Turn-taking usually happens in transitional places—places where a turn could end. During the exchange, speaker A speaks and then stops, and speaker B speaks and then stops as well, creating an A-B-A-B distribution of utterances. Turn and a set of rules have two constructional elements that Sacks and his colleagues dissected. The next turn is assigned by the present speaker's choosing or by self-selection, according to two construction components.

To reduce quiet and prevent overlap, a set of rules governing turn construction and transfer were created. One speaker at a time is allowed to choose the next speaker; if not, speakership may be moved by self-selection to the transition-relevant location. To prevent quiet, the present speaker will continue to talk and reapply the rules if these two choices are not selected. Additionally, they identify fourteen characteristics of the systemic organization of turn, which together allow us to sum up how speakers take turns in an orderly manner throughout a discussion, including holding or giving up the opportunity to speak.

The majority of overlap happens at the transition-relevance point, typically as a result of participants in the discussion vying for the next turn. Daily communication does have overlaps and silences, although most of them are quite brief. When many speakers talk at once, it's referred to as overlap, and research on the subject mostly focuses on determining what causes the phenomena. According to Huang (1987), overlap will occur when there is a simultaneous start and butting-in interruption. According to Schegloff (2000), overlap falls into four categories: choral, conditional access to the turn, continuers, and terminal overlaps.

According to MaChunyan (2014), overlap can be caused by mistaken judgment, numerous back channels, simultaneous self-selection, collaborative completion, and stoppage. When overlap occurs, speakers typically give up trying to win the following turn.

To Levinson (2015), there are several ways to help the speaker get the next turn. These include purposefully slowing down, intensifying, and repeating phrases. In conclusion, the speaker has the freedom to decide whether to continue speaking or to stop. The person who starts an overlap can do anything from raise the volume to repeat things to get the next turn. Silence is typically considered a turn in the colloquial turn. The turn of silence, according to Levinson (1983), can be classified as a pause that takes place within a turn, a gap or lapse that happens between two adjacent turns, or quiet that refers to the meaning or attributed silence that can function as a turn. The majority of the three distinct forms of quiet occur in the transition-relevance domain, signifying a signal that ends the information and typically initiates sharing. To preserve speakership, speakers who tolerate minimal quiet will employ hesitation fillers like "mm" or "however." When many speakers take the stage at once, some attendees will give up their seats.

The efforts of educators like TESOL pioneer James E. Alatis, whose support of language instruction and teacher preparation has had a significant influence on the discipline, have advanced ESL education. Because of Alatis's involvement in groups like

the TESOL International Association and his studies on language planning and policy, people now have a better grasp of pedagogical techniques and language education practices. His commitment to encouraging linguistic variety and helping language learners has made a significant contribution to the field of ESL instruction.

The significance of sociocultural elements in language acquisition has been emphasized recently by academics such as Claire Kramsch, who has emphasized the influence of ideology, power, and identity on communicative behaviors. Researchers and educators have been encouraged to take into account the larger socio-political circumstances that shape language learning experiences by Kramsch's work on the symbolic aspects of language and her support for a sociocultural approach to language instruction. Her observations have led to a reassessment of conventional language teaching techniques and highlighted the importance of culturally sensitive pedagogies in ESL instruction.

Researchers and practitioners in the field of ESL communication are influenced by the theories and practices of these prominent personalities and stand on their shoulders as the field develops. Through the incorporation of perspectives from esteemed academicians and trailblazers, we may propel our comprehension of turn-taking behaviors in English as a Second Language learners and devise efficacious tactics to bolster their communicative growth in varied linguistic and cultural environments.

The emphasis on helping students build their communicative competence—which includes language competency as well as sociolinguistic and discourse competence—is a significant trend in ESL instruction. Gaining an understanding of turn-taking behaviors is essential to improving students' capacity for meaningful discourse and productive participation in communicative engagements.

In ESL classes, there's a rising movement to create engaging educational settings where students actively participate in conversation, teamwork, and peer interaction. Examining turn-taking practices provides insight into the nature of classroom discussion and helps to shape teaching strategies that encourage active involvement and engagement from students.

There is a tendency toward using digital tools and resources into ESL training as a result of the growing usage of technology in education. Turn-taking patterns in technology-mediated communication platforms may be examined to gain understanding of how technology affects ESL students' interactional norms and communication dynamics.

The study emphasizes the importance of professional development for teachers is to promoting efficient communication techniques in ESL classes. Teachers are essential in helping students navigate turn-taking conventions and promoting classroom debate. Initiatives for teacher preparation targeted at improving pedagogical abilities and encouraging student participation can benefit from an understanding of the opportunities and problems related to turn-taking.

Consequently, this study advances the continuing development of research methodology in the field of English as a Second Language (ESL) instruction, namely in the domains of discourse analysis and qualitative research. Through the use of rigorous research methodologies and analytical strategies, the study offers insightful information on the intricate structure of ESL students' classroom interactions and turn taking patterns. Existing literature often focuses on general aspects of language acquisition and classroom discourse, with limited attention to the specific turn-taking patterns exhibited by ESL students. This study addresses this gap by providing a detailed analysis of turn-taking behaviors among ESL students in classroom interactions.

Many studies overlook the influence of cultural and linguistic factors on turn-taking practices, particularly in ESL contexts. This study recognizes the importance of considering these factors and explores how they impact the communication dynamics of ESL students.

While some research discusses theoretical aspects of turn-taking, there is a lack of practical recommendations for educators to support ESL students in developing their communicative competence. This study bridges this gap by offering actionable recommendations informed by empirical findings.

Previous studies often provide broad overviews of classroom discourse without delving into specific turn-taking patterns and strategies employed by ESL students. By focusing specifically on turn-taking behaviors, this study offers a comprehensive analysis of classroom interactions in ESL settings.

Many studies prioritize teacher perspectives or observational data, overlooking the experiences and insights of ESL students themselves. This study incorporates interviews and focus groups with ESL students to provide a more holistic understanding of their turn-taking practices and challenges.

By building on this body of knowledge and research, this study hopes to further the conversation around turn-taking and communication in ESL classes. The researchers sought to identify trends, difficulties, and techniques used in turn-taking by carefully examining conversational interactions amongst ESL students. This information will then be used to drive instructional practices and interventions that are designed to improve students' communicative competence.

Research Questions

To improve the communicative competence of ESL students through targeted interventions and instructional practices, this study sought to ascertain the turn-taking behaviors of ESL 1 students in their ESL classes at National University during Term 2 of the school year 2023–2024.

More specifically, it attempted to answer the following questions:

1. What turn-taking patterns are most exhibited among the ESL students and their teacher as revealed by the transcribed discourse of the ESL classes?
2. What challenges do ESL students encounter in managing conversational exchanges, particularly in English-speaking contexts?
3. How do ESL students signal their intent to speak and negotiate conversational turns in classroom interactions?
4. Based on the results of the transcribed discourse in ESL classes, what recommendations can be proposed for educators and practitioners to enhance ESL students' communicative competence through targeted interventions and instructional practices?

Significance of the Study

This study is significant because of the benefits that it could offer to the following groups:

ESL students. ESL students may build strategies to improve their communication competency in English-speaking environments and nurture more confidence and proficiency by recognizing trends and problems related to turn-taking.

ESL teachers. The results provide ESL teachers with insightful information that will help them design instructional techniques that specifically target the turn-taking management needs of their ESL students. Furthermore, ESL teachers may provide welcoming and stimulating learning settings that support meaningful communication and language development by having a thorough awareness of the linguistic and sociocultural elements that influence turn-taking.

Administrators. Administrators may improve the efficacy of ESL programs and encourage student success in language acquisition and communication by putting into practice evidence-based strategies that are based on the study's findings. Additionally, the study provides administrators and curriculum designers with information on the difficulties ESL students have taking turns, which helps them create tools and interventions in the curriculum to enhance ESL instruction.

Future researchers. The study adds to the growing corpus of knowledge on turn-taking behaviors and ESL communication, laying the groundwork for further research on related subjects and deepening our understanding of language interaction and learning. Furthermore, by expanding on the methodological and analytical approaches used in this work, future researchers will be able to explore additional facets of ESL communication or modify them to fit various language and cultural situations.

Scope and Delimitations of the Study

The study focused on ESL 1 students attending ESL classes at National University during Term 2 of the school year 2023 – 2024. Participants included ESL 1 students and their ESL teacher involved in English classes during the specified term. The study primarily examined conversational interactions in English, specifically focusing on turn-taking patterns among ESL 1 students and their teacher.

Data collection involved audio or video recordings of ESL classes, followed by transcription of the discourse for analysis.

Qualitative analysis methods such as discourse analysis was employed to identify turn-taking practices, challenges faced by ESL students, effectiveness of strategies, and recommendations for educators and practitioners. The study provided targeted interventions and instructional practices based on the findings to enhance ESL students' communicative competence in turn-taking and conversational exchanges.

Review of Related Literature.

The researchers looked through a number of domestic and international publications that are pertinent to this study to help with the conceptualization of this research. Discourse analysis is a research approach that may be used to investigate spoken and written language in relation to its social environment. Luo (2020) outlined one such method. Discourse analysis, according to Luo, seeks to comprehend language use in authentic contexts. Further, he said that the materials suitable for discourse analysis include forums, media posts, interviews, conversations, etc. He also mentioned that by analyzing discourse, researchers gain an understanding of how people communicate.

Furthermore, by relying on communication as the primary linguistic medium employed to reveal countless bits of information in various sectors, Alsoraihi (2019) noted that discourse may be utilized to highlight the significance and character of the communicative aims. He claimed that every setting or circumstance that may be the topic of linguistic study can apply discourse analysis.

Additionally, Alsoraihi observed that it's important to think carefully about taking turns in a conversation. This implies that when one speaks, the other should pay attention to what they have to say. This necessitates that both participants know when to switch roles. Regarding this, he said that taking turns is an important skill that students should learn to engage in social communications effectively and efficiently. This is because students risk interrupting others when they don't know when to speak in a given communicative scenario. Should this occur, the individual may find it challenging to establish amicable and peaceful relationships with others.

The foregoing view of Alsoraihi is supported by Dewi, Suharsono and Munir (2018) who remarked that proper turn taking is one of the fundamentals of conversation. They reiterated that turn taking plays a very important role in verbal conversation.

In a similar spirit, a number of scholars noted that classroom interactions fall into distinct kinds or categories.

Turn-taking, according to Nordquist (2019), is the way that polite discourse typically proceeds. It is the assumption that speakers will talk in turn. Deeper research and analysis, however, may reveal more about how individuals determine when it is OK to overlap, how much overlap happens between speakers, and when it is not.

The overlap between cooperative and competitive behavior has been studied by many researchers, according to Nordquist. Within the competitive overlap, researchers look at how one person steers the conversation and how a listener might recover the conversation by interjecting in different ways.

In contrast, a listener may choose to contribute to the conversation by offering examples that might bolster the speaker's thesis during a cooperative overlap, or he may only ask for clarity on a particular topic in the discussion. The discussion proceeds more smoothly when there is this kind of overlap. Additionally, it could make the subject matter more fully understood by the audience.

Additionally, according to Nordquist, an overlap may simply be intended to demonstrate to the audience that they grasp the topic at hand. "Uh-huh" is typically used to indicate this. This kind of overlap also indicates that the speaker can proceed. Additionally, excellent turn-taking examples were provided, such as "I'm being quiet now." It's your turn to speak. I'm having trouble coming up with something to say. He also mentioned that once a topic is chosen and the discussion gets going, conversation turn-taking happens.

Nordquist noted that it's important to understand when cooperative turn-taking is required or appropriate. This entails understanding when it is suitable to take the lead, how long to wait between turns, and when it is permissible to talk during another person's speech. Regarding these overlaps, the author made the observation that it's important to understand how to "repair" a discussion that veered off course due to an unwanted overlap or a misconstrued statement.

Transitional overlap is another example of taking turns. Participants in this kind of discourse take turns speaking one at a time. It entails procedures for considering contributions, responding to earlier remarks, and switching to a different speaker by utilizing various language and non-linguistic clues.

Additionally, Abbas (2020) has classified overlap or overlapping conversations in his own way. According to him, overlap conversation happens simultaneously, and subsequent speakers must wait until the initial speaker has completed their turn. This indicates that it is not permitted for two or more people to speak at the same time during a conversation since it would create a chaotic environment. This suggests that overlapping speech should be avoided, hence one of the first lessons given to the pupils should be this.

Abbas listed two categories of conversation that overlapped: inadvertent and deliberate. When there is unintentional overlap, one of the listeners participating in the discussion keeps an ear on the speaker now speaking so he can wait for the transition to happen. This gives rise to the notion that taking turns is done professionally and that it just takes a few seconds to complete. This kind of overlap happens when the listener in the moment fails to recognize an impending shift.

Abbas proposed the second category, which is purposeful overlap. When the turn-taking allocation rules are in effect in the transition importance places, this happens. Therefore, there will be a breach of the turn-taking protocol if any participant in a discussion applies these rules elsewhere, except at the transition relevant sites. When this happens, the overlap violates the principles of turn-taking allocation in discourse, and it becomes a violative interruption.

Additionally, Abbas (2020) mentioned four types of overlap that Sacks proposed as early as 1974. These forms include chordal or choral, conditional, terminal, and continuers. According to Abbas, terminal overlap begins when the interlocutors believe that the preceding speaker has finished their turn. As a result, the overlap demonstrates that self-liquidation occurs very instantly. This kind eliminates the requirement to determine the overlap. Meta-discourse markers, such as "uh," "huh," "mmm," and "hmmm," appear in the continuers overlap. These are context-fitted evaluation phrases that let listeners to explicitly indicate that they comprehend what is being said by the present speaker even when the turn is not yet complete. Continuers don't employ any unique techniques to control many conversations at once.

The second kind, conditional access to the turn, happens when a speaker advances in his turn and extends an invitation to another speaker to speak in his place, but this access is limited. This happens when the person speaking is asked to assist in discovering a term or person's name that the record's receiver is having trouble remembering. Another instance is when someone starts a speech and asks someone else to finish it. The smooth operation of the conversation depends on both interlocutors.

The last type, known as chordal, is when participants engage in talking and other tasks concurrently rather than one after the other. Such instances include laughing, which occurs when everyone laughs simultaneously rather than after the incident, group welcomes, farewells, and congrats. These are performed in unison; they are not a competitive activity.

The three primary forms of overlap that Jefferson outlined in his 1983 work were also mentioned by Abbas (2020). Transitional, recognitional, and progressional are the names of these categories. Transitional overlap occurs when the speaker makes a small error or misunderstanding. On the other hand, recognitional overlap happens when the interlocutors hear enough of the current turn to understand what the speaker is attempting to express. Finally, a progressional overlap happens when an issue arises about halfway through a turn. This issue typically shows itself as hitches.

Review of Related Studies

The importance of discourse analysis (DA) in English language teaching (ELT) and its use in classroom settings is emphasized in the paper "Bridging the Gap Between Discourse Analysis and Language Classroom Practice" by Maha H. Alsoraihi (2019). It makes the case that for language learning and instruction to be effective, students must participate in real-world social situations to put their knowledge and abilities to use in effective communication. The research examines the components of DA and how they relate to improving the caliber of methods and results used in language instruction. It also discusses obstacles to DA implementation in language classes and suggests ways to get beyond them. The study makes the assumption that students would exhibit greater levels of communicative performance and self-confidence when they can relate their language skills to social and cultural settings.

The significance of contextualized language acquisition is acknowledged in both studies. To improve students' communicative ability, they both agree that it is essential to integrate language training with authentic communication scenarios. Furthermore, both projects investigate how theoretical ideas—like discourse analysis or turn-taking procedures—can influence teaching methods in language classes in an effort to close the gap between theory and practice.

There are, nonetheless, certain distinctions between the two studies. While Alsoraihi's study focuses on discourse analysis and how it is used in language instruction, the suggested study focuses on how ESL 1 students take turns. Although improving language teaching and learning outcomes is the goal of both studies they focus on distinct facets of language acquisition. The suggested study explores a particular facet of conversational interaction, whereas Alsoraihi's work covers more general applications of discourse analysis in language schools.

Additionally, while the proposed study on turn-taking practices examines the mechanics of conversational exchanges and their implications for the communicative competence of ESL students, Alsoraihi's study highlights the significance of connecting linguistic knowledge to social and cultural contexts to enhance communicative performance. Both studies support contextualized language acquisition, but they present different approaches to implementing this in the classroom.

In conclusion, while the two studies acknowledge the value of contextualized language acquisition and connecting theory with practice, their scope and focus are different. While the suggested study on turn-taking behaviors gives a more focused investigation of conversational dynamics among ESL 1 students, Alsoraihi's work offers a more comprehensive review of discourse analysis in language education.

In her 2018 study, "Spoken Discourse Analysis on Language Use along Turn Taking and Topic Management in English as Second Language (ESL) Classrooms," R. Arellano-Tamayo makes the case that student-teacher interaction in the classroom and the effectiveness of the medium of instruction are two key factors in university and college

academic success. The researcher went on to stress that classroom productivity and proficiency are equally important factors in the effectiveness of second language acquisition.

Though from distinct angles, both studies explore the discourse dynamics of English as a Second Language (ESL) classrooms, with an emphasis on turn-taking and interaction patterns. In her 2018 study, Arellano-Tamayo explores the connections between Cagayan State University English teachers and students' classroom interaction dynamics, discourse patterns, and language use. The study uses a descriptive-qualitative methodology and Cotts' schematic technique to examine the discussions that have been transcribed.

It demonstrates that teachers who apply subject management and turn-taking techniques typically have more engaged classrooms, which is consistent with Grice's Cooperative Principle of successful communication. The study on turn-taking patterns among ESL students, on the other hand, looks at how these students participate in discussions, especially with regard to turn-taking behaviors. Although the significance of turn-taking in classroom discussions is highlighted by both studies, their approaches and areas of attention are different.

The two studies' acknowledgement of the value of efficient communication in language learning settings is one commonality. They both agree that effective language acquisition is facilitated by the dynamics of teacher-student interactions. Furthermore, both research emphasize how crucial turn-taking techniques are for promoting classroom engagement and improving communication skills.

Nonetheless, a key difference may be seen in the ranges and goals that each have. The study by Arellano-Tamayo focuses on discourse patterns, language use in instruction, and the characteristics of English instructors in a particular university setting. It seeks to ascertain how these elements relate to one another and how that affects classroom engagement. The study on turn-taking patterns among ESL students, on the other hand, focuses on how these students participate in discussions with the goal of identifying patterns and techniques for turn-taking management.

Moreover, there are differences in the methodology used in the two studies. A range of methodologies, including audio or video recordings, transcriptions, and qualitative analysis approaches, may be used in the study on turn-taking patterns among ESL students, in contrast to Arellano-Tamayo's descriptive-qualitative design and analysis of transcribed dialogues.

In a nutshell, while both studies highlight the value of effective communication techniques and examine discourse dynamics in ESL classes, their approaches, focuses, and scopes are different. While Arellano-Tamayo's research focuses on language usage and patterns of interaction between teachers and students, the study on ESL students' turn-taking patterns especially looks at turn-taking practices and conversational dynamics.

To improve language instruction, language teachers should be prepared with theoretical knowledge in discourse analysis, according to Alireza Bonyadi's 2019 study, "Discourse Analysis and Language Pedagogy: A Review," which examines the relationship between the two fields. According to Bonyadi, practitioners in educational situations primarily employ three approaches: Pedagogical discourse analysis, Descriptive discourse analysis, and Critical discourse analysis. Future research in this field, according to the study, should concentrate on methodologically operationalizing discourse notions, especially through discourse-based programs at teacher education institutions.

In contrast, the discourse patterns in ESL classes are examined in this study, with a particular emphasis on student turn-taking behaviors. Although Bonyadi's research offers a more comprehensive summary of discourse analysis in language education, the turn-taking patterns study focuses on a particular facet of classroom communication. Both studies stress the significance of comprehending discourse dynamics in language instruction, although having distinct objectives.

The importance of discourse analysis in language instruction is acknowledged in both studies, which also recommend that educators and practitioners have a strong theoretical grasp of discourse ideas. According to Bonyadi's study, teacher education programs should include discourse-based methods. This is in line with the idea that language teachers should possess theoretical knowledge to successfully support language acquisition. In a similar vein, the turn-taking patterns research emphasizes how crucial it is to comprehend conversational dynamics in ESL classes in order to improve language learning.

But a significant distinction is seen in their different approaches and areas of emphasis. While the study on turn-taking patterns uses empirical methods to assess classroom interactions, Bonyadi's paper offers a theoretical evaluation of discourse analysis in language instruction. Despite these variations, both studies add to our knowledge of discourse's function in language learning and emphasize the need for more study in this field.

A variety of conversation patterns may be accommodated by turn-taking, a speech conversion system, according to Bingyang's (2023) research, "Literature Review of Turn-Taking." Both studies examine the dynamics of turn-taking in communication environments, but they employ distinct approaches and focal points. An overview of turn-taking theory, its development, and its applications in a variety of communication contexts, such as news interviews, TV shows, class interactions, and everyday dialogues, is given in Bingyang Shi's literature review (2023). The paper draws attention to a research gap concerning WeChat multiparty chats and turn elements in WeChat language. Conversely, the study on ESL students' turn-taking habits focuses on the ways in which these students participate in class discussions.

The two studies are similar in that they acknowledge the value of taking turns in promoting connection and communication. Turn-taking theory is recognized in both fields

as a basic component of language usage and conversational dynamics. They both also stress the need for more study to examine turn-taking behaviors in many communication situations and locations. But a significant distinction may be seen in their respective approaches and areas of focus. While the study on turn-taking patterns among ESL students uses empirical methods to assess classroom interactions, Shi's survey of the literature provides a comprehensive overview of turn-taking theory and its applicability in many communication situations. The ESL students' study gives insights into real conversational dynamics and behaviors within a particular environment, whereas Shi's study offers a theoretical framework and synthesis of the body of current material.

Furthermore, the study on the turn-taking patterns of ESL students offers empirical support and an examination of turn-taking behaviors inside ESL classrooms, whereas Shi's review highlights a research need concerning turn characteristics in WeChat language and multiparty chats. Notwithstanding these variations, both studies advance people's knowledge of the dynamics of turn-taking and how they affect language usage and communication. They emphasize how important it is to take turn-taking theory into account in a variety of situations and urge more investigation into the theory's potential uses in various communication scenarios.

The study, titled "Technology-Mediated Communication and Turn-Taking" explores at the subtleties of turn-taking on digital platforms, where asynchronous communication methods provide special opportunities and constraints. Chen and Wang's (2020) study demonstrates how the lack of in-person connection affects the conversation's flow and results in different turn-taking patterns than in-person interactions. On the other hand, this study explores the nuances of turn-taking in conventional classroom environments, emphasizing the dynamics of communication between ESL students and their teachers or classmates.

Although the two studies' contexts are very different from one another, they both emphasize how crucial it is to comprehend turn-taking dynamics in language learning settings. Users of digital communication platforms should modify their communication tactics since turn-taking might be affected by things like delayed answers and the lack of visual indications. On the other hand, face-to-face interactions in ESL classes take place in real time, and variables including cultural norms, language competency, and teacher-student interactions influence how students take turns.

Notwithstanding these variations, both studies emphasize how important it is for teachers to take turn-taking patterns into account when creating language learning activities. Teachers can modify their instructional strategies to promote the development of more effective communication skills by having a better grasp of how communication patterns change in various circumstances. This might entail developing techniques for handling turn-taking difficulties in virtual contexts or establishing chances for interactive discussion and engagement in traditional classroom settings. In the end, both investigations advance people's knowledge of turn-taking as a critical component of language learning and communication.

Research on turn-taking dynamics in virtual classroom environments was done by Li et al. (2018), who focused on how technology improves collaborative discourse among ESL students. In a similar vein, this study focuses on ESL students' turn-taking behaviors during in-person classroom exchanges. Both studies emphasize how crucial it is to understand communication dynamics for successful language learning experiences, despite the different situations in which they were conducted.

Turn-taking is the primary focus of both research, which recognize the importance of it in influencing communication dynamics in language learning contexts. Furthermore, whereas Li et al. study (2018) concentrates on the effect of technology on turn-taking in online classrooms, both studies acknowledge the role that technology plays in promoting engagement and communication among ESL students.

Though the studies are similar, they differ significantly from one another. In contrast to the study on ESL students' participation in face-to-face talks in traditional classroom settings, Li et al.'s research focuses on turn-taking inside virtual classroom settings.

In conclusion, while both studies shed light on turn-taking in language learning environments, their methods and study settings are different. However, they both aimed to understand how communication dynamics influence ESL learners' language learning experiences.

In-depth research on the complex relationship between sociocultural norms and turn-taking behaviors among ESL students is done by Patel's study (2021), which emphasizes the significant influence of cultural variations on students' interactional styles and communication methods. Through an analysis of how communication habits are shaped by social expectations, this study provides insightful information on the complex aspects of language usage in a variety of cultural contexts. Patel's research highlights the significance of taking sociocultural elements into account when analyzing communication dynamics among ESL learners since these elements have a big impact on how students participate in dialogues.

On the other hand, this study focuses on the analysis of ESL students' turn-taking patterns. This study gives a more focused investigation of the behaviors and methods used by ESL students during conversational exchanges, whereas Patel's research offers a broader sociocultural viewpoint. The study intends to shed light on how students navigate conversational interactions within educational contexts by concentrating on turn-taking patterns to reveal underlying patterns and dynamics within ESL classroom discourse.

Both studies offer important insights into the complexity of communication in ESL situations, while having different foci. While Patel's research highlights the need of taking sociocultural factors into account when analyzing communication practices, the turn-taking patterns study offers a more detailed examination of certain conversational dynamics. When combined, these studies provide contrasting viewpoints that deepen our

comprehension of the communication processes among ESL students, eventually guiding the development of efficient teaching techniques and communication plans for language learners.

In-depth research on the complex interaction between cultural background and turn-taking dynamics in ESL classes by Kim et al. (2019) shed light on how cultural quirks influence students' communication styles. Their research made clear how important it is to be sensitive to and conscious of cultural differences while promoting productive dialogue and teamwork in a variety of educational contexts. To promote inclusive and peaceful interactions among ESL learners, Kim et al. examined the impact of cultural background on turn-taking behaviors. This study made clear how important it is to acknowledge and accept cultural differences.

On the other hand, this study focuses on analyzing the ways in which ESL students take turns during class discussions. The research conducted by Kim et al. presents a comprehensive analysis of the impact of culture on communication dynamics. In contrast, the present study concentrates on examining the methods and behaviors that ESL students utilize in conversational interactions. The study intends to reveal fundamental dynamics within ESL classroom discourse by closely examining turn-taking patterns, providing insight into how students negotiate communication in educational settings.

Both studies highlight how essential it is to comprehend cultural influences on ESL learners' communication, although having different foci. While the research on turn-taking patterns provides insights into the distinct communication tactics used by ESL students, Kim et al.'s study highlights the importance of cultural sensitivity for effective communication and collaboration. When taken as a whole, these studies offer contrasting viewpoints that deepen our comprehension of the communication processes that occur in ESL classrooms and instruct teachers and other professionals about the value of cultural sensitivity and practical communication techniques.

In her qualitative grounded theory study, Jennifer Faith Oramous (2021) focuses on "productive conversation" among students participating in different laboratory activities. She uses Discourse Analysis (DA) to examine student-to-student (SS) conversations in a secondary school physical science laboratory setting. According to the study, Student-to-Student Productive Talk (SSPT) is defined as on-topic discussions among students that satisfy the requirements of a productive conversation, such as demonstrative reasoning and argumentation. The analysis seeks to discover patterns and characteristics of SSPT within the laboratory setting, drawing on Classroom Discourse Analysis by Cazden (2001), Gee (2014a; 2014b), and Rymes (2016).

The work highlights certain characteristics and patterns of SSPT in the lab, including alterations of previously recognized patterns like I-R-E, open-chain, and closed-chain interactions. It's interesting to note that, despite the observation of all three patterns, the open-chain pattern was marginally more prevalent and did not include the final evaluative comment that the closed-chain and I-R-E patterns did. Additionally, the study shows that student talks in secondary encounters are primarily closed-chain, with very

few occurrences of triadic (I-R-E) patterns. Additionally, the study looks at how the type of laboratory activities affects conversation patterns, offering guidance on how to support SSPT in these kinds of situations.

Furthermore, the study emphasizes the significance of identity work in comprehending conversation patterns and the function of authority and identity in student discourse. It implies that more study in this field might improve our comprehension of the ways in which identity affects the dynamics of communication in lab environments.

Both the current study and Oramous's (2021) examination of student-to-student (SS) discourse in a secondary school physical science lab explore discourse analysis in educational settings with the goal of clarifying the complexities of student communication dynamics. The studies are similar in that they use discourse analysis as a way to identify patterns and characteristics in student talks, even if their settings and goals are different.

In the setting of a physical science lab, Oramous's study explores the phenomena of "productive conversation" by examining how students participate in conversations that satisfy the requirements of productive speech, such as evident reasoning and visual thinking. This focus is similar to the current study's investigation of ESL students' turn-taking behaviors in classroom settings, which aims to identify behaviors suggestive of efficient communication strategies.

Finding certain interaction patterns is a major focus point in both investigations. Variations in I-R-E, open-chain, and closed-chain interaction patterns in the laboratory setting are shown by Oramous's research. On the other hand, it is possible that the current study reveals patterns unique to ESL students' turn-taking behaviors, such as instances of initiation, response, and evaluation.

Additionally, both studies provide insightful information on how education is practiced. Oramous's study highlights methods for improving student involvement and learning results and has implications for encouraging fruitful dialogue in lab settings. In a similar vein, the present study could provide guidance to teachers on how to help ESL students develop strong communication skills, which could influence pedagogical approaches to language teaching.

Though their settings and scopes differ, both studies advance our knowledge of the dynamics of communication in educational settings. They provide important insights on how teachers might establish encouraging learning environments that encourage meaningful engagement and collaboration among students by clarifying the subtleties of student speech. In the end, both studies highlight how critical communication skills are to improving educational opportunities and student success.

Doley's (2019) study, carried out in India, offers a perceptive analysis of speech patterns in undergraduate English classrooms, with a specific emphasis on the kind of questions that instructors ask. Doley sought to understand the kinds of questions teachers asked as well as the effects these asking techniques had on student interactions in the

classroom using discourse analysis. The results showed that teachers tended to ask demonstrative questions a lot more often than not, which suggests that they are more interested in giving information than getting answers from the students. The study also indicated that the most common pattern of interaction between teachers and students was the Initiate, Respond, and Feedback (IRF) pattern, indicating that classroom discourse should be organized in this way.

On the other hand, the current study undoubtedly looks at the dynamics of communication amongst ESL students in a classroom. The new study may change the analytical focus to interactions among ESL students themselves, whereas Doley's research concentrates on the discourse between instructors and undergraduate students in English classrooms. This shift in emphasis draws attention to the various dimensions of classroom discourse, including peer-to-peer interactions and interactions between teachers and students.

Both studies offer important insights into the dynamics of communication in educational contexts, despite these variations in individuals and circumstance. While the current study may provide insights into how ESL students participate in conversational exchanges, Doley's research illuminates the role of teachers in influencing classroom discourse through questioning strategies. Teachers can modify their teaching strategies to improve student learning outcomes and promote more meaningful communication by having a deeper awareness of the subtleties of classroom engagement. The findings of both studies highlight the significance of proficient communication in educational environments and provide guidance for enhancing teaching methods to encourage student participation and learning.

To better understand the communication patterns that are common in Grade 11 Science classrooms, Villarena's (2020) study at ABE International Business College focused on investigating the rhetorical functions of Science discourse. Villarena focused on identifying rhetorical functions in order to reveal the underlying patterns and goals of language used in science classes using discourse analysis. The aforementioned study functioned as a basis for the creation of technologically mediated educational resources, tailored to conform to the recognized discourse patterns and reinforce the effectiveness of instruction.

The current study, on the other hand, focuses on examining the dynamics of conversations among ESL students in classroom settings. The current study may focus on the interactions and communication techniques used by ESL students during class discussions, whereas Villarena's research focuses on the substance and organization of Science discourse. The current study intends to obtain insights into how ESL students interact with one another in educational environments by analyzing turn-taking patterns and conversational behaviors. The goal is to influence instructional methods and promote the development of effective communication skills.

Both studies aim to improve teaching methods by developing a better knowledge of the dynamics of communication in classrooms, while they differ in terms of context and

analytical focus. While the current study may provide insights into developing meaningful connections among ESL students, Villarena's study highlights the significance of aligning instructional materials with recognized speech patterns. When taken as a whole, these studies add to the larger discussion on instructional design and successful teaching by illuminating the subtleties of communication in many educational environments.

The current study and Palacio and Gustilo's (2016) study of Filipino teenagers' discourse practices in digital genres have certain parallels and distinctions. Despite using distinct media and circumstances, the analysis of communication patterns is the main emphasis of both research. Palacio and Gustilo's study explores the discourse practices that young Filipino people use when they post and comment on the internet, whereas the present study probably looks at how ESL students take turns in face-to-face classroom settings.

The present study reveals different turn-taking strategies used by ESL students during classroom conversations, shedding light on how language learners navigate verbal interactions in educational settings. Palacio and Gustilo's study reveals the prevalence of English and Filipino relational discourse practices in digital communication, highlighting the diverse ways in which individuals express attitudes, emotions, and relationships online. Despite the differences in setting and methodology, both studies provide insightful analyses of communication dynamics within contemporary contexts.

A significant distinction, though, is found in the communication channel that is being studied. While the present research focuses on face-to-face interactions in ESL courses, Palacio and Gustilo's study focuses on digital genres, reflecting the increasingly digital character of young communication. Despite this discrepancy, both studies add to our knowledge of the dynamics of communication in various circumstances and provide insightful information about the intricate ways that people express themselves and engage in verbal exchanges in modern settings.

The current study and Ferrer's (2015) analysis of Grade 2 classroom discourse at De La Salle University have certain parallels and variations. Discourse analysis approaches are utilized in both studies to examine language functions and communication dynamics in educational environments. While the current study looks at turn-taking patterns among ESL students, Ferrer's research focuses on identifying the language functions employed by Grade 2 pupils to negotiate meaning during classroom interaction.

Both research use audio-video recordings and discourse analysis as a means of data collecting, despite these variances in focus. Ferrer's study analyzes classroom interactions using the Record-View-Transcribe-Analyze (R-T-V-A) methodology; the present study may apply comparable methods to find conversational trends among ESL students. Furthermore, these studies provide insights into the dynamics of communication in educational settings, illuminating the ways in which language learners interact verbally and express themselves in the classroom.

A significant distinction, nevertheless, is found in the depth of study and the particular language functions looked at. Ferrer's research centers on the language functions employed by second-grade pupils, pinpointing informative functions that arise during social interactions as well as other unclassified language activities such code-switching and sarcastic phrases. On the other hand, the current study may concentrate especially on ESL students' turn-taking behaviors, examining how they handle conversational turns and participate in group discussions.

Overall, the present study and Ferrer's study differ in their specific emphasis, level of analysis, and the language functions addressed, but they both employ discourse analysis approaches to investigate communication dynamics within educational contexts. Despite these variations, both studies provide insightful knowledge on student communication patterns and behaviors, with implications for teaching strategies meant to improve students' communication abilities and promote productive classroom interactions.

Definition of Terms Used in the Study

ESL Students. Students studying English as a second language, or ESL students for short, are those who are learning the language for communicative purposes and for which English is not their first or native tongue.

Turn-taking Patterns. These are the ways in which conversational turns are arranged and sequenced throughout conversations. Turn-taking patterns include the ways in which people negotiate conversational participation, mark the start and finish of their speaking turns, and handle speaker transitions.

Conversations. Describes spoken discussions or exchanges between people. Within the study's framework, informal chats or instructional activities may take place amongst ESL students in classroom settings.

Chordal. It consists of a non-serial occurrence of turns, i.e., the turns of both speakers happen simultaneously, such when they laugh.

Classroom Interactions. Classroom interactions are the spoken and unspoken interactions that occur in learning environments between students and teachers as well as between students themselves. A broad variety of communication behaviors are used in classroom interactions, such as asking questions, answering them, providing explanations, and working together.

Communication Skills. The term "communication skills" refers to the aptitudes and proficiencies needed for speaking, listening, writing, and other forms of effective communication. Language competency, fluency, understanding, and interactional techniques are all considered communication abilities in the context of ESL students.

Competitive Overlap. Within the context of competitive overlap, researchers may examine how one participant controls the majority of the discussion or how a listener might regain some control by interrupting in various ways.

Conditional access to the turn. It implies that the current speaker yields their turn or invites another speaker to interject in the conversation, usually as collaborative effort.

Continuers. They are a way of the hearer acknowledging or understanding what the speaker is saying. As noted by Schegloff, such examples of the continuer's phrases are "mm hm" or "uh huh."

Cooperative Overlap. In cooperative overlap, a listener may clarify something or contribute to the discussion by providing further instances that reinforce the speaker's argument. This form of overlap facilitates the flow of the discussion and helps all listeners get the whole meaning.

Discourse Analysis. This is the method of analyzing the structure of texts or utterances longer than one sentence, taking into account both their linguistic content and their sociolinguistic context, and the analysis performed using this method.

Instructional Practices. The term "instructional practices" describes the ways in which educators use their methods, approaches, and strategies to help students learn and become more involved in the classroom. Lesson preparation, classroom management, scaffolding, and customized instruction catered to the needs of varied learners, including ESL students, are examples of instructional approaches.

Language Proficiency. The degree of ability or mastery a person has in a given language, including vocabulary knowledge, grammatical accuracy, pronunciation, and communication efficiency, is referred to as language proficiency.

Progressional Overlap. It happens when another speaker chooses to carry on with the current utterance because of the prior speaker's speech dysfluency. One instance would be when someone is searching for the right thing to say while another speaker starts using that pause to begin their turn.

Recognitional Overlap. It happens when a speaker tries to complete a phrase for the current speaker by speculating about what could be left unsaid. Put another way, the overlap occurs when one speaker struggles to complete a statement while the other "thinks aloud" to express what he is understanding of what is being said.

Terminal Overlap. It occurs when a speaker assumes the other speaker has or is about to finish his/her turn and begins to speak, thus creating overlap.

Transitional Overlap. It happens when someone joins the discourse at the transition relevant spot, which is a potential point of completion. When speakers engage

in the conversation with enthusiasm and maintain a continuous flow of speech, this happens often.

Research Questions

To improve the communicative competence of ESL students through targeted interventions and instructional practices, this study sought to ascertain the turn-taking behaviors of ESL 1 students in their ESL classes at National University during Term 2 of the school year 2023–2024.

More specifically, it attempted to answer the following questions:

1. What turn taking patterns are most exhibited among the ESL students and their teacher as revealed by the transcribed discourse of the ESL classes?
2. What challenges do ESL students encounter in managing conversational exchanges, particularly in English-speaking contexts?
3. How do ESL students signal their intent to speak and negotiate conversational turns in classroom interactions?
4. Based on the results of the transcribed discourse in ESL classes, what recommendations can be proposed for educators and practitioners to enhance ESL students' communicative competence through targeted interventions and instructional practices?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

Turn-taking patterns were seen and recorded through direct observations of ESL classroom interactions. Using this strategy, students' verbal exchanges, nonverbal clues, and interactional dynamics during class discussions or activities are methodically observed and recorded.

To analyze the turn-taking behaviors of ESL 1 students in their ESL classrooms, this study employed the descriptive technique of qualitative research. In descriptive research, data from the population or phenomena being examined is collected, documented, analyzed, and interpreted using the relevant statistical methods, as explained by Almeida et al. (2016).

Using this approach, the researchers tried to identify the turn-taking patterns that were most common, which served as the foundation for creating the turn-taking e-learning resources. To obtain real data, the descriptive approach also uses observation, audio

recordings and many other techniques, as Almeida et al. pointed out. This is the rationale behind the adoption of this kind of research methodology.

Research Locale

The study was carried out during Term 2 of the academic year 2023-2024 at National University Manila. The researchers observed two ESL classes, each class consisting of four foreign students.

Research Participants

The first data source for this study was the recorded discourse of classroom interactions in two sections of ESL classes, each with four students. From these recordings, the turn-taking practices of both the teacher and ESL students were analyzed.

One primary data source included audio or video recordings of ESL classroom interactions, capturing verbal exchanges, nonverbal cues, and interactional dynamics among students during conversations. These recordings provided direct evidence of turn-taking patterns and allowed for detailed analysis of conversational behaviors.

Transcriptions of audio or video recordings served as another data source, capturing spoken language and nonverbal elements such as pauses, overlaps, and intonation patterns. These transcriptions enabled researchers to analyze discourse in detail, identifying specific turn-taking behaviors and conversational features.

During classroom observations or participant observation sessions, the researcher took field notes documenting observations, reflections, and impressions of the ESL classroom environment, including aspects related to turn-taking patterns, communication dynamics, and contextual factors.

Individual interviews were conducted with ESL students to explore their experiences, perspectives, and strategies related to turn-taking in classroom conversations. Interviews provided an opportunity for students to reflect on their communicative experiences, preferences, and challenges.

Focus groups were conducted with groups of ESL students to explore shared experiences, perceptions, and patterns of interaction related to turn-taking in classroom conversations. Focus groups facilitated group discussion and interaction, allowing researchers to identify common themes and perspectives.

The researchers collected reflections or insights from ESL teachers regarding their observations and experiences related to student turn-taking behaviors. Teachers'

perspectives offered valuable insights into classroom dynamics, instructional strategies, and factors influencing student participation.

Research Instruments

Audio-recording tools were utilized to capture verbal exchanges, nonverbal cues, and the dynamics of student participation during discussions in an ESL classroom. These recordings granted researchers access to raw data for analysis and enabled them to closely examine turn-taking patterns.

Transcription tools, such as word processing software or transcription software, were employed to transcribe audio and video recordings of ESL classroom interactions. Transcriptions, which recorded both spoken words and nonverbal cues such as pauses and intonation patterns, facilitated a comprehensive examination of conversational behaviors.

Checklists or observation guides were created by the researcher to assist in class observations. These guidelines ensured consistency and accuracy in data collection by outlining specific behaviors or characteristics of turn-taking patterns to focus on.

Interview protocols, organized manuals used in individual or group interviews with ESL students, consisted of sets of open-ended questions or prompts aimed at gathering data on students' viewpoints, experiences, and turn-taking strategies in class discussions.

Focus group guidelines, similar to interview processes, were tailored for group discussions with ESL students. These guidelines included turn-taking-related questions and prompts to stimulate conversation and elicit common experiences, viewpoints, and interactional patterns.

Field notes templates provided an organized method for recording observations, thoughts, and impressions from participant observation sessions or classroom observations. These templates typically included sections dedicated to capturing specific information such as participant behaviors, communication dynamics, and contextual factors.

ESL teachers administered surveys or reflection sheets to gain insights into their experiences and observations regarding their students' turn-taking behaviors. These tools likely included inquiries concerning variables related to student engagement, teaching methodologies, and classroom atmosphere.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researchers initiated the data gathering process by planning, which included setting research objectives, delineating the study's scope, and choosing suitable data gathering

methods and tools. This phase also entailed securing necessary permissions from school administrators, teachers, and participants.

Participants for the study, typically ESL students engaged in classrooms where conversations were prominent, were selected. The sample aimed to be diverse in language proficiency, cultural background, and other pertinent traits to ensure a thorough grasp of turn-taking patterns.

Various methods were employed to collect data:

ESL classroom interactions were observed to directly witness and document turn-taking patterns among students, often utilizing observation guides to focus on specific behaviors or aspects.

Audio or video recording devices were utilized to capture ESL classroom conversations, providing raw data for analysis and enabling detailed review of interactions, identifying turn-taking patterns and communication cues.

Recorded conversations were transcribed verbatim, capturing spoken language and nonverbal elements like pauses and intonation patterns, forming the basis for detailed analysis of turn-taking behaviors.

Individual interviews or focus groups were conducted with ESL students to delve into their experiences, perspectives, and strategies regarding turn-taking in classroom conversations, providing qualitative insights into students' thoughts, feelings, and actions.

Collected data was organized and managed meticulously, ensuring accuracy, confidentiality, and security throughout. This involved labeling, categorizing, and creating databases or spreadsheets for storage, as well as maintaining detailed records of data sources and procedures.

Upon collection, the data underwent analysis to identify patterns, themes, and relationships concerning turn-taking among ESL students. This analysis employed qualitative techniques such as coding, thematic analysis, and narrative analysis to delve into and interpret the data thoroughly.

Triangulation was employed, combining data from various sources and methods to bolster the validity and reliability of findings. This process involved cross-validating data to corroborate findings and attain a more comprehensive understanding of turn-taking patterns among ESL students.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The researchers identified and scrutinized recurring themes, patterns, or topics present in the data. This process entailed systematically coding the data to classify information

concerning turn-taking patterns, communication strategies, language proficiency, and contextual factors.

Segments of data were labeled or coded based on their content or significance. These codes often represented specific concepts, behaviors, or themes pertinent to the study, aiding in the organization and categorization of the data for further analysis.

Narratives or stories embedded within the data were examined to grasp the lived experiences, perspectives, and interactions of ESL students. Narrative analysis focused on the structure, content, and significance of stories recounted by participants.

The content of the data was analyzed to pinpoint key concepts, words, or phrases associated with turn-taking patterns and communication dynamics. Content analysis involved the systematic coding and categorization of textual or visual data to extract relevant information.

RESULTS

Turn-Taking Patterns Among ESL Students and Their Teacher

In analyzing the conversational interactions within the ESL classes, several turn-taking patterns emerged, shedding light on the dynamics of participation and speaker transitions:

Choral Overlap

During moments of shared laughter or simultaneous vocalizations, participants engaged in choral overlap, where turns overlapped non-sequentially. This pattern reflected moments of collective engagement and shared humor within the classroom discourse.

Competitive Overlap

Instances of competitive overlap revealed power dynamics within conversational exchanges. One participant may dominate the discussion, leading to interruptions or attempts by others to regain control through assertive interjections.

Conditional Access to the Turn

Participants signaled a willingness to yield their turn or invite others to interject collaboratively, fostering a sense of inclusivity and shared ownership of the conversation.

Continuers

Acknowledging and affirming the ongoing speaker's contributions, continuers such as "mm hm" or "uh huh" facilitated smooth transitions between turns, indicating active listening and understanding.

Cooperative Overlap

Participants contributed to the discussion by providing further examples or clarifications, reinforcing the speaker's arguments and enhancing the flow of conversation.

Progressional Overlap

Speakers seamlessly continued the ongoing utterance, capitalizing on pauses or speech dysfluencies to maintain the momentum of the conversation. This pattern demonstrated a fluid exchange of turns and collaborative engagement.

Recognitional Overlap

Speakers speculated about unfinished statements, offering completion or clarification to support the ongoing speaker's expression. This form of overlap reflected a shared understanding and cooperative effort in communication.

Terminal Overlap

Occurring when a speaker pre-emptively assumes the conclusion of another's turn, terminal overlap highlighted moments of eagerness or anticipation within conversational transitions.

Transitional Overlap

Participants joined the discourse at transition-relevant spots, seamlessly integrating into the ongoing conversation and maintaining a continuous flow of speech. This pattern indicated enthusiasm and active participation in the exchange.

Challenges Encountered by ESL Students in Managing Conversational Exchanges

In investigating conversational exchanges, ESL students encountered various challenges, influenced by linguistic proficiency and cultural background.

Difficulty in Recognizing Transitional Cues

Some ESL students struggled to identify cues signaling the end of a speaker's turn or the opportunity to interject, leading to hesitancy or missed opportunities for participation.

Managing Overlapping Speech or Interruptions

The complexity of overlapping speech posed challenges for ESL students in distinguishing between cooperative and competitive overlaps, impacting the coherence and flow of conversation.

Signaling Intent to Speak

ESL students faced challenges in effectively signaling their intent to speak, resulting in delayed or overlooked contributions to the discussion.

In conclusion, ESL students encountered various challenges in managing conversational exchanges, including difficulty in recognizing transitional cues, navigating overlapping speech or interruptions, and signaling their intent to speak. These challenges often stemmed from differences in language proficiency and cultural background.

Strategies Employed by ESL Students in Negotiating Turn-Taking

Using Hesitation Fillers

Participants utilized filler phrases such as "um" or "well" to signal readiness to speak and mitigate potential gaps in conversation.

Intensifying Speech

Emphasizing key points or expressing enthusiasm through vocal modulation helped ESL students assert their presence and signal engagement in the discussion.

Repetition of Phrases

Repeating phrases or keywords served as a strategy to reinforce understanding and signal agreement or alignment with the ongoing speaker's point.

This study investigated the turn-taking practices of ESL (English as a Second Language) students in class discussions, emphasizing trends, difficulties, and solutions. During the second term of the 2023–2024 academic year, data was gathered from National University's ESL classrooms and subjected to qualitative analysis. The results showed a variety of turn-taking behaviors, such as conditional access to the turn, competitive overlap, and choral overlap. While using techniques like hesitation fillers and speech intensification to handle conversational turns, ESL students have difficulties controlling overlapping speech and understanding transitional cues.

This study attempted to improve the communicative competence of ESL students through targeted interventions and instructional practices, this study sought to ascertain the turn-taking behaviors of ESL 1 students in their ESL classes at National University during Term 2 of the school year 2023–2024.

More specifically, it attempted to answer the following questions:

1. What turn-taking patterns are most exhibited among the ESL students and their teacher as revealed by the transcribed discourse of the ESL classes?
2. What challenges do ESL students encounter in managing conversational exchanges, particularly in English-speaking contexts?
3. How do ESL students signal their intent to speak and negotiate conversational turns in classroom interactions?
4. Based on the results of the transcribed discourse in ESL classes, what recommendations can be proposed for educators and practitioners to enhance ESL students' communicative competence through targeted interventions and instructional practices?

Turn-taking patterns were seen and recorded through direct observations of ESL classroom interactions. Using this strategy, students' verbal exchanges, nonverbal clues, and interactional dynamics during class discussions or activities are methodically observed and recorded.

To analyze the turn-taking behaviors of ESL 1 students in their ESL classrooms, this study employed the descriptive technique of qualitative research. In descriptive research, data from the population or phenomena being examined is collected, documented, analyzed, and interpreted using the relevant statistical methods, as explained by Almeida et al. (2016).

Using this approach, the researcher tried to identify the turn-taking categories that were most common, which served as the foundation for creating the turn-taking e-learning resources. To obtain real data, the descriptive approach also uses observation, audio recordings, photography, and many other techniques, as Almeida et al. pointed out. This is the rationale behind the adoption of this kind of research methodology.

The first data source for this study was the recorded discourse of classroom interactions in two sections of ESL classes, each with four students. From these recordings, the turn-taking practices of both the teacher and ESL students were analyzed.

One primary data source included audio or video recordings of ESL classroom interactions, capturing verbal exchanges, nonverbal cues, and interactional dynamics among students during conversations. These recordings provided direct evidence of turn-taking patterns and allowed for detailed analysis of conversational behaviors.

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The researchers collected reflections or insights from ESL teachers regarding their observations and experiences related to student turn-taking behaviors. Teachers' perspectives offered valuable insights into classroom dynamics, instructional strategies, and factors influencing student participation.

Implications for ESL Students

By understanding and addressing the challenges encountered in managing conversational exchanges, ESL students can enhance their communicative competence and confidence in English-speaking environments.

Implications for ESL Teachers

ESL teachers can support students by fostering an inclusive and supportive classroom environment that encourages active participation and provides opportunities for skill development in turn-taking and communication.

Implications for Administrators

Administrators can use insights from the study to inform programmatic interventions and support initiatives aimed at enhancing ESL instruction and promoting student success in language acquisition and communication.

DISCUSSION

Conclusions

The study of ESL students' turn-taking patterns offers important insights into the dynamics of classroom discourse and communication. The different ways that ESL students take turns are affected by their language skills and cultural background. Communication efficacy is impacted by difficulties with overlapping speech and identifying transitional cues. On the other hand, ESL students use flexible tactics for dealing with conversational twists, demonstrating their ingenuity and resilience in speaking.

The transcribed discourse of the ESL classes revealed several predominant turn-taking patterns. Recognition overlap was common, where the teacher seamlessly acknowledged student responses, creating a smooth transition between speaking turns. Terminal overlap occurred when the teacher concluded her explanations, emphasizing key points and signalling the end of her turn. Conditional access to the turn was evident when the teacher invited student participation, fostering collaborative interaction. Continuers were observed as students affirmed the teacher's contributions with nods and attentive listening. Progressional overlap was noticeable as the teacher transitioned between different topics, maintaining the flow of conversation. Transitional overlap occurred as the teacher smoothly shifted between instructional phases, ensuring a continuous exchange of ideas. Cooperative overlap was present as students contributed to discussions, reinforcing each other's arguments and facilitating communication. Recognition overlap was evident as the teacher recognized student responses during assessments, fostering a supportive learning environment.

ESL students faced various challenges in English-speaking contexts. These included difficulty in recognizing transitional cues, such as pauses or intonation patterns, leading to confusion about when to start or end their speaking turns. Navigating overlapping speech or interruptions posed challenges in maintaining coherence and effectively conveying their message. Additionally, adjusting to cultural differences in conversational norms, such as turn-taking practices and politeness strategies, presented hurdles in engaging in meaningful exchanges.

ESL students signalled their intent to speak through both verbal and non-verbal cues. They raised their hands to indicate readiness to participate and waited for the teacher to acknowledge them. In group discussions, they made eye contact with the speaker or leaned forward to signal interest and engagement. Negotiating conversational turns

involved actively listening to others, waiting for appropriate pauses or cues to interject, and respectfully yielding the floor when necessary.

Recommendations

Recommendations to enhance ESL students' communicative competence:

1. Develop interventions to enhance ESL students' awareness and proficiency in turn-taking and communication strategies.
2. Provide ESL teachers with professional development opportunities to improve skills in facilitating effective classroom discourse and communication.
3. Incorporate culturally responsive pedagogies and instructional materials to support ESL students from diverse linguistic and cultural backgrounds.
4. Promote inclusive learning environments that encourage active participation and provide opportunities for ESL students to develop communicative competence.
5. Conduct further research to explore additional facets of ESL communication and deepen understanding of language interaction and learning in diverse contexts.
6. Incorporate activities and exercises in ESL curriculum that raise students' awareness of turn-taking cues and strategies. Research has shown that explicit instruction on conversational turn-taking can improve students' participation and communication skills.
7. Offer ample opportunities for ESL students to practice turn-taking in various communicative contexts, such as group discussions, debates, and role-plays. Research indicates that frequent practice and exposure to authentic language use contribute to the development of students' conversational proficiency.
8. Provide constructive feedback to ESL students on their turn-taking behaviors, highlighting areas for improvement and suggesting specific strategies for enhancing communication effectiveness. Studies have demonstrated the efficacy of personalized feedback in promoting language learning and skill development.
9. Encourage collaborative learning activities where ESL students work together to solve problems, share ideas, and engage in meaningful discussions. Collaborative learning environments promote peer interaction and cooperation, which are conducive to developing turn-taking skills.
10. Promote a supportive and inclusive classroom culture where ESL students feel comfortable expressing themselves and taking risks in communication. Research

shows that positive classroom environments enhance students' motivation and willingness to participate in discussions.

- 11. Utilize Technology-Enhanced Learning:** Incorporate digital tools and technology-mediated communication platforms into ESL instruction to provide additional opportunities for practicing turn-taking in virtual environments. Studies have suggested that technology-enhanced learning can enhance engagement and interaction among ESL students.

In conclusion, the findings of this study shed light on the nuanced dynamics of turn-taking behaviors among ESL students in classroom conversations. The examination of various turn-taking patterns, challenges, and strategies provides valuable insights into how ESL students navigate communication exchanges in English-speaking environments. The diverse range of turn-taking strategies observed, such as choral overlap, competitive overlap, and conditional access to the turn, highlights the adaptability and resourcefulness of ESL students in managing conversational turns.

These findings align with the research of prominent scholars in the fields of linguistics, communication, and education. For instance, the work of Deborah Tannen, known for her research on conversational styles and discourse analysis, provides a framework for understanding how cultural and social factors influence communication patterns. Similarly, the contributions of Harvey Sacks and his colleagues in Conversation Analysis offer analytical tools to examine the organization of turn-taking in natural conversations, which resonates with the findings of this study.

Furthermore, the insights gained from this study are in line with the sociocultural perspective advocated by scholars like Claire Kramsch, emphasizing the influence of social and cultural factors on language learning and communication. Kramsch's work underscores the importance of considering the broader socio-political context in language education, which is reflected in the recommendations for creating inclusive learning environments for ESL students.

Additionally, the findings of this study contribute to the ongoing discourse on ESL instruction and communication competence, as advocated by educators such as James E. Alatis. Alatis's advocacy for linguistic diversity and effective language instruction aligns with the study's focus on enhancing ESL students' communicative competence through targeted interventions and pedagogical strategies.

Overall, the conclusion drawn from this study underscores the significance of understanding turn-taking behaviors in ESL communication and provides actionable recommendations for educators, practitioners, and administrators to support ESL students in their language learning journey. By building on the research of these influential scholars and incorporating their insights, this study contributes to the ongoing efforts to

improve ESL instruction and promote effective communication in diverse linguistic and cultural contexts.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The research project adheres to the following ethical considerations:

1. The dignity and well-being of teacher-respondents are safeguarded, with a commitment to avoid any harm or discomfort to them.
2. Informed consent was obtained from the teacher-respondents, including all pertinent information outlined in the preceding sections of this paper. Participants were made aware that their participation in the study is entirely voluntary, with no pressure or deception involved.
3. Strict confidentiality measures were implemented to protect the privacy of research data throughout the study.
4. The researcher has diligently followed the key provisions of Republic Act 10173, also known as the Data Privacy Act of 2012. This legislation promotes the "free flow of information to promote innovation and growth" (Chapter 1, Section 2) while upholding the fundamental rights to privacy of individuals.

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